

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B244
Date: 19 September 2006
Take Off 09:06:08Z
Landing: 13:47:13Z
Flight Time 4h41m05s

Campaign: AMPEP

Operating Area: South and East coasts of England

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	DFL
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	DFL
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	DFL
4	Mission Scientist	Eiko Nemitz	CEH Edinburgh
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics / CCM2	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
8	Filters	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
9	Bag Filler 1	Colin MacDonald	CEH Edinburgh
10	Bag Filler 2	Debbie Polson	CEH Edinburgh
11	PERCA	Dan Brookes	University of Leicester
12	WAS	Stephen Humphrey	University of East Anglia
13	NOXY	Dave Stewart	University of East Anglia
14	AMS	Keith Bower	University of Manchester
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16			
17			
18			
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20			

Flight Track:

B244 Track 19-SEP-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b244
 Date: 19 Sept 2006
 Project: AMPEP
 Location: S & E coasts

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
085112		INU	0.36 kft	128	To Navigate
090608		T/O	0.98 kft	301	Cranfield 090608
091311	093859	Run 1	10.0 kft	252	NOXY Cals
092422		Video	9.1 kft	329	Start RFC & DFC
094640	100350	Run 2	0.95 - 0.96 kft	234	1k' , Q1016
100606	101252	Run 3	5.5 kft	138	Over Devon
101253	101611	Profile 1	5.5 - 2.2 kft	130	Q1009,2k'
101611	101712	Run 4	2.2 - 2.1 kft	126	2k', Q1019
101712	101929	Profile 1	2.1 - 0.42 kft	127	2k-500'
101929	102036	Run 5	0.42 - 0.44 kft	126	500'
102036	102116	Profile 1	0.44 - 0.15 kft	126	500-250'
102116	102215	Run 6	0.15 - 0.13 kft	126	250'
102229	102322	Run 6	0.17 - 0.14 kft	087	wings level now
102329	102504	Profile 2	0.16 - 0.88 kft	081	250-1k', Q1017
102504	124519	Run 7.1	0.88 - 1.1 kft	094	1k'
103539		Event	0.88 kft	070	WP 45
104619		Event	0.90 kft	041	Eqwerilus Leader ship
104922		Event	0.89 kft	046	WP 44
105430		Video	0.90 kft	092	Change Tapes
105958		Heimann	0.91 kft	093	Cal 12-18C
110346		Event	0.87 kft	073	WP 43
111222		Event	0.91 kft	055	Q1016
111532		Event	0.89 kft	024	WP 42
113548		Event	1.0 kft	357	Q1015
113722		Heimann	0.98 kft	358	Cal 12-18C
114350		Event	0.97 kft	328	Abeam WP 40
115219		Event	0.98 kft	304	Abeam WP87by 4nm
115555		Event	1.0 kft	328	Q1014
120223		Event	1.1 kft	327	Q1012
121306		Event	1.1 kft	315	Abeam WP80
122347		Event	1.1 kft	313	Q1009
122445		Video	1.1 kft	314	Change Tapes
122841		Heimann	1.1 kft	313	Cal 15-10C
122943		Event	1.1 kft	336	WP 79
124519	124639	Profile 3	1.1 - 0.46 kft	335	1k-250', End @WP77
124804	124904	Run 8	0.46 - 0.45 kft	332	250'
124904	124926	Profile 4	0.55 - 0.71 kft	179	250-500'
124926	125023	Run 9	0.71 - 0.68 kft	176	500'
125024	125157	Profile 4	0.69 - 2.1 kft	179	500-2k'
125158	125259	Run 10	2.1 kft	179	2k'
125300	125446	Profile 4	2.1 - 3.9 kft	177	2k'-FL38
125446	125550	Run 11	3.9 - 3.8 kft	178	FL38
125550	125810	Profile 4	3.8 - 6.0 kft	178	
125811	125910	Run 12	6.0 kft	169	
125911	130326	Profile 4	6.0 - 10.0 kft	170	
130326	133616	Run 13	10.0 kft	178	NOXY Cals
134713		Land	0.34 kft	354	Cranfield
135056		Shutdown	0.33 kft	308	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B244 Track 19-SEP-06

EGTC -> EGTE - Overview

NavData Cycle 2006-9 Expires: Thursday, 28 September 2006.

Scale: 1:2478347 (1 inch = 33.99 naut mi). Printed on 19 Sep 2006

JEPPESEN

FliteStar 9.160

Sortie Brief: AMPEP

Flight Number : B244

Mission Scientist: Eiko Nemitz, CEH

Date : 19-September-2006

Outline schedule:

06:00 – Power to aircraft – warm-up
08:00 – Briefing
09:15 – Clear aircraft and security check
09:30 – Doors close
10:00 – Take off Cranfield
14:30 – Land Cranfield
15:00 – Debrief
17:00 – Power down

Location: A coastal transect of the South and East Coast of England

Sortie Aims: To measure the UK pollutant budget of a range of gases and aerosols leaving the UK in WSW airflow over the UK. The objective, in addition to measuring the export fluxes of pollutants is to derive the chemical processing (gas/aerosol partitioning & oxidation state) of the air mass.

Sortie Summary: The budget measurements will be obtained by flying off the South and East coasts along a coastal transect beginning in the Bristol Channel to sample background air off the coast of Cornwall. The transect of the UK outflow begins along the English Channel heading East to Dover then North to the point where airflow off the land stops, which according to current forecasts is North Yorkshire. Vertical profiles (250 – 6000 ft) once upwind in the Bristol channel and downwind of the source region off the Northumberland coast on the Southbound leg will provide the vertical structure in concentration and meteorology. These should clearly extend into the free troposphere (Mission Scientist to verify from profiles of humidity, temperature and CO. These measurements will establish the upwind concentration, the concentration differential at the top of the boundary layer and the concentration in the outflow from the source region. Flight ceiling will be 10000ft. Cabin pressure will be maintained at 1200ft, to minimize expansion of the Tedlar bags.

Sortie Detail with approx timing

- a) Take off Cranfield 10:00 and climb to 10000 ft for transit east to operating area, towards waypoint 37 in the Bristol Channel; cleaning of filter system (purge without filters loaded); NOXY calibration. Descend to 1000 ft as soon as possible into Bristol Channel, initiated over land; start of filter pack background run.
- b) T+35: Cross Devon/Cornwall at 5000 ft.
- c) T+45: Stop of filter-pack background run. Descending upwind profile down to define the boundary layer structure off the coast with 1 min sampling at each height (2000, 500, 250)
- d) T+60: Return to 1000 ft for sampling..
Start of filter run No 1. Start of continuous bag sampling (1 bag every min) continue all the way up the east coast. Approximately 30-minute filter pack runs from here (called by Mission Scientist)

Monday 18 September 2006 00UTC ©ECMWF Forecast t+036 VT: Tuesday 19 September 2006 12UTC
 Surface: 2 metre temperature / 30 Metres Wind

Instrumentation strategies & issues:

Filter sampling: Filters will be taken throughout the flight. Filter pack 1 will contain a Teflon filter for trace metal analysis. Filter pack 2 will contain a Teflon prefilter (for major ion analysis), a nylon filter (for HNO₃ & HCl) and an acidified paper filter (for NH₃). Filters will be changed approximately every 30 minutes or when flight conditions change (as advised by the Mission Scientist). Filters are preloaded into cartridges, which need to be handled with gloves and stored in sealed bags immediately. Filter sampling will be suspended during vertical profiles and resumed when FL10 is re-attained. During breaks, filter packs will be isolated by switching off the pump (to minimise evaporation of volatile aerosol components). During initial transfer to the operating area, the sampling should be set to sampling at the earliest opportunity after T/O, without filters loaded (to aid cleaning of the system). On the transit back, a set of filters should be loaded into the filter packs, without sampling, to provide a field blank value.

AMS: The AMS will be operated continuously during the flight. Monitored masses will include m/z 16, 18, 28, 30, 43, 44, 46, 57 and 64. The inlet remains closed until airborne to minimize contamination during taxi take-off.

Core Chemistry: CO, SO₂, NO and NO₂ will be measured continuously during the flight. CO will be calibrated every 30 minutes at 1000ft.

Tedlar bags: Tedlar bags will be filled at a flow rate of 6 lpm, filling a bag over a duration of 30 s. Bags will be filled every 3 minutes upwind and every minute downwind of the source region and during each leveling out for a profile step. Bags should be filled to about 90% of their capacity to maximise sample volume. The cabin pressure will be tightly controlled. Bags from first part of flight can be stored in cargo hold for second part.

Aerosol & cloud physics: CN and PCASP are operated continuously.

Core meteorology & state: Are recorded as standard. Video recording of front facing and downfacing cameras.

TDL for CH₄ and CO₂: to be operated

NOXY: will be operated during the flight. HNO₃ channel will be tested and is not considered reliable.

PERCA: will be operated

Quick-look data: pressure height, lat, long, temp, RH, CN, SO₂, NO, NO₂, O₃, CO

Analysis chart valid 00 UTC TUE 19 SEP 2006

Analysis chart valid 06 UTC TUE 19 SEP 2006

19/09/06 14:00 radar

EIEB51 MSG 10.8 micron Infrared Image 19 Sep 2006 1400 UTC

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 19 Sep 2006 1400 UTC

Mission Scientist's Debrief

Flight No : B244

Date : 19/09/2005

Name : Eiko Nemitz, CEH

1. Assessment of the flight

The flight proceeded according to the planned route and after T/O at 9:06 started with a transit to the Bristol Channel at FL100 for NO_x calibration and purging of the filter system (without filters loaded). After sampling at 1000 ft for about 15 mins in the Bristol Channel (from 09:47 – 10:03), Devon was crossed at an altitude of 5500 ft. On the ascend scattered cloud was penetrated between 2500-4000 ft. A filter-pack run was started in the Bristol channel and continued during this crossing. At the English Channel coast a stepped down profile was flown (5500, 2000, 500, 250, 1000), followed by a run anticlockwise along the coast, at 1000 ft, up to the Farne Islands. Here a further stepped profile was flown (1000, 250, U-turn at 250, 500, 2000, 3800, 6000, 10000), followed by a transit flight back at FL100 for NO_x calibration and filter-pack background run. Filters were exposed along the Channel, and two further runs up along the East Coast.

Concentrations were very clean in the Bristol Channel, with neither NO_x, SO₂ nor CO showing major gradients. Small plumes were encountered on reaching the English Channel although shipping activity was low in the west part. Further plumes of NO_x and SO₂ were seen along the channel, which could sometimes be associated with individual ships. Along the Channel, background levels started to increase just before Dover (most clearly seen in CO), with an associated decrease in O₃. The London plume was clearly sampled in the outflow and its location matched the model prediction well. The Teesside / Midlands plume was smaller with a more variable ratio of the different components. Towards the end of this plume, concentrations of CO and SO₂/NO_x decreased suddenly, coinciding with a decrease in PCASP counts and improvement in visibility, indicating that the north part of the country was under the influence of a different air mass.

There were several noteworthy instrumentation issues during this flight:

- a) The AMS signal was dubious and post-flight assessment needs to reveal whether useful data were obtained (the post-flight calibration appears to have worked).
- b) The pressure in the WAS bottles did not appear to go down during sampling and they may not have been filled.
- c) There was an issue (possible electrical connection) with the TDLAS – the harddisk failed.
- d) The CPC (part of the AMS setup) was not logged for a short time (probably about 30 minutes) as the logging program crashed.
- e) The flow rates for the filters were very irregular and sometimes larger through the filter holder with the smaller number of filters (and thus smaller resistance). Post-flight checks will need to reveal whether there is a problem with the mass flow meter.
- f) The NO_x instrument had a high background initially.
- g) Fluctuations were observed on the PCASP concentration, especially towards the later part of the flight. This may be due to the lowest channels which are usually discarded in the data analysis.

2. Summary of the weather conditions

There was a high-level light broken Cirrus layer, together with local scattered cloud, which was stronger in the Bristol Channel, almost absent over the English Channel and the North Sea. A brief shower was encountered at 12:19 and another spotted inland at 12:13. Visibility was hazy with an ill-defined horizon in the SW and improved throughout the flight to the NE.

The wind was steady from WSW with wind speeds at 1000 ft ranging between 6 and 15 m/s.

To add screengrabs to this two column document click on the Internet Explorer window you want to save,

ALT + PRNT SCR (one key in from top left on keypad)
 To paste into this document press CTRL + V

Tephi on T/O:

Nox profile on T/O:

SO2 profile on T/O

CO Profile on T/O:

Tephi descent into Bristol Channel:

CO2 profile

Nox profile descent Bristol channel:

SO2 profile descent Bristol Channel:

Tephi out of Bristol Channel:

CO2 profile out of Bristol Channel:

Nox profile out of Bristol Channel:

SO2 profile out of Bristol Channel:

Descent profile into English Channel – Tephi:

Descent profile into English Channel – CO:

Descent profile into English Channel – NOx:

Descent profile into English Channel – SO2:

Along Channel (up to WP 43):

East Coast To WP 77:

Profile NE – Tephi:

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.244**.....

 Date 19/09/2006.....

 Page 2 of 4...

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:17	P1 coast	2000 → 500ft			end of run CO calib. triggered by air stroke abort → revert to old cal.
10:19	S	500ft			
10:20	P1 coast	500 → 250			
10:21	G	250ft			
10:23	P2 coast	250 → 1000ft			GWs @ 246°
10:25	F	1000			end of P2 hazy poorly defined horizon
10:26	FP2				start of run 2
10:31					ship plume?; O3 temporarily set to 0
10:46					"Equator's leader" Roll on/off foggy ship plume view sky
10:49				WP 44	12 m/s @ 272° end of FP line 2
11:04				WP 43	high NO _x , SO ₂ & CO; clear plume
11:08					downwind of Shaw power station by about 30 nautical miles
11:11	FP3				10 m/s @ 247°
11:14					several container ships underneath bow to left
11:15				WP 42	
11:17					bow shipping plumes fire due N (9-10 miles) 2 miles SW of Starbon

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.244**.....

 Date 19/09/06.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:23					into London plume, lower O ₃ , higher CO
11:27					downwind of several ships London plume followed by ship plumes (downwind Felixstowe)
11:52				WP 87	8 w/s @ 270° lightly scattered cumulus horizon better than in Channel
11:59					Passing fishing fleet elevated CO₂ (regional)
12:00					end end of FP3
12:04					CO plume downwind of (ball). 15 w/s @ 266°
12:05				S ⁹ W ¹⁸ /0.12	different air mass? CO ₂ drops, O ₃ rises visibility much improved!
12:05	FP4				start of FP4 run
12:13				WP 80	showers inland → responsible for dir in cone?
12:19					going through small showers
12:26					Widemouth plume
12:29				WP 79	11 w/s @ 255°
12:34					fishing boat (large modern) plume
12:37					in plume of visible power station on coast

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.244**.....

 Date 19/09/2006.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:45	end of Run 7			WPTT	Profile 3 start 1000 → 250
12:46	P3 end 250ft.				U-turn
12:49	R9	500ft			
12:50	P4	→ 2000ft			
12:51	R10	2000ft			14 m/s @ 250°
12:52	P4	→ 4000ft			
12:54	R11	3800ft			just below scattered cloud base
12:55	P4	→ 6000ft			cloud tops at 5500
12:58	R12	6000ft			
13:03	R13	FL100			start of FP Run 5 & NOxy cal
13:36	end R13				end of Run R13 & FP Run 5 descend to Cranfield
					light scattered convective cloud
					FP field blank banded
Instrument issues:					
					- temp sampling outcome not certain
					- AMS AMS data questionable
					- TOVS TOVS data lost (AMS failed)
					- some AMS - CRC was not logged
					- flow rates filter questionable.
					- fluctuation on total PCASP cone ⇒ smallest channels?

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B175

Date: 19/09/06	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 07:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:07:19	795	0.06	1													FL020 PCASP Vref = 6.5	
09:07:51	542	0.05	1													FL030	
09:08:12	745	0.06	1													FL040	
09:08:46	735	0.06	1													FL050cmd1d	
09:18:00	1728	0.06	1													FL100 (Heaters on)	
09:20:00	1740	0.06	1													FL100	
09:22:00	1536	0.06	1													FL100	
09:24:00	1210	0.06	1													FL100	
09:26:00	1388	0.06	1														
09:28:00	1480	0.06	1														
09:30:00	1450	0.06	1													FL100	
09:32:00	1410	0.06	1													FL100	
09:34:00	1274	0.06	1														
09:40:20	1259	0.06	1													FL080	
09:41:20	1590	0.06	1													FL070	
09:41:50	1811	0.06	1													FL060	
09:42:24	1455	0.06	1													FL050	
09:43:03	2391	0.07	1													FL040	
09:45:10	1485	0.06	48													FL020	
09:46:25	1289	0.06	48													FL010	
09:46:40	1056	0.06	48													Start of RUN 1 AT FL010	
09:48:00	664	0.06	48													FL010	
09:50:00	509	0.06	48													FL010	
09:52:00	525	0.07	48													FL010	
09:54:00	398	0.06	48													FL010	
09:56:00	447	0.06	48													FL010	
09:58:00	469	0.06	49													FL010	
10:00:00	535	0.06	49													FL010	
10:01:00	468	0.06	49													Turn at Waypoint 37 @ FL010	
10:03:00	430	0.06	49													End of Run 2 at FL010	
10:03:49	388	0.06	49													FL010	
10:04:25	566	0.07	50													FL020	
10:04:48	389	0.07	59													FL030	
10:50:20	352	0.06	60													FL040	
10:05:45	330	0.06	60													FL050	
10:06:06	359	0.06	60													Start or Run 3 at FL055	
10:08:00	555	0.06	60													FL055	
10:10:00	838	0.06	60													FL055	
10:12:00	702	0.06	68														
10:12:54	1082	0.06	68													End R3 Start P1 at FL055	
10:13:28	1150	0.06	68													FL050	
10:14:20	1086	0.06	69													FL040	
10:15:15	970	0.06	69													FL030	
10:16:16	1119	0.07	69													FL020 INTERRUPT P1	
10:17:14	720	0.07	69													FL020 P1 (HEATERS OFF)	
10:18:22	1300	0.06	69													FL010	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B175

Date: 19/09/06	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 07:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:19:35	729	0.06	69													FL005 INTERRUPT P1	
10:20:43	544	0.07	69													P1	
10:21:15	714	0.06	69													End P1 Start R6	
10:22:20	843	0.06	69													250FT AGL (wings level)	
10:23:21	599	0.06	69													END R6, START P2	
10:24:20	438	0.06	69													FL005	
10:25:04	484	0.06	69													FL010 END P2, START R7	
10:27:00	699	0.06	69														
10:29:00	702	0.06	69														
10:31:00	822	0.06	69														
10:33:00	824	0.06	69														
10:35:00	667	0.06	69														
10:37:00	602	0.06	70														
10:40:00	633	0.06	70														
10:43:00	733	0.06	70														
10:45:00	662	0.06	70														
10:48:00	885	0.06	70														
10:50:00	903	0.06	70														
10:52:00	909	0.06	70														
10:55:00	821	0.06	70														
11:00:00	795	0.06	71														
11:03:00	962	0.07	71														
11:05:00	984	0.06	71														
11:07:30	994	0.07	71														
11:10:00	839	0.06	71														
11:13:00	855	0.06	71														
11:15:00	885	0.07	71														
11:18:00	801	0.06	71														
11:20:00	885	0.06	71														
11:22:00	843	0.07	71														
11:25:00	867	0.06	71														
11:27:00	865	0.07	71														
11:29:00	892	0.06	71														
11:32:00	961	0.06	71														
11:34:00	944	0.06	71														
11:36:00	974	0.06	71														
11:38:00	842	0.06	71														
11:40:00	735	0.06	72														
11:44:00	988	0.07	72														
11:46:00	1040	0.06	72														
11:48:00	1130	0.06	72														
11:50:00	1098	0.06	72														
11:52:00	1002	0.06	72														
11:54:00	979	0.06	72														
11:56:00	1091	0.06	72														
11:58:00	1070	0.06	72														

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B175

Date: 19/09/06	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 07:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:00:00	1107	0.06	72														
12:02:00	980	0.07	72														
12:04:00	1075	0.07	72													PLUME on CO too.	
12:06:00	1023	0.07	72														
12:08:00	540	0.06	72													Coincident drop in CO, rise in O3	
12:10:00	690	0.06	72														
12:12:00	900	0.06	72														
12:14:00	1064	0.06	72														
12:16:00	997	0.06	72														
12:18:00	845	0.06	72														
12:22:00	702	0.06	72														
12:24:00	586	0.06	72														
12:26:00	820	0.06	72														
12:28:00	870	0.06	72														
12:30:00	1040	0.06	72														
12:32:00	1045	0.06	72														
12:34:00	1051	0.06	72														
12:36:00	1046	0.06	72														
12:38:00	1088	0.06	73														
12:40:00	1027	0.06	73														
12:42:00	1054	0.06	73														
12:44:00	1051	0.06	73														
12:45:21	895	0.06	73													End Run8, start Profile 3 at FL010	
12:46:28	572	0.06	73													End P3 at 250FT AGL	
12:48:00	734	0.06	73													250FT	
12:48:49	675	0.06	73													Start Run 9 at 500FT	
12:50:25	775	0.06	73													End R9, start P4	
12:50:50	473	0.06	73													FL74010	
12:51:59	747	0.06	73													FL020, start Run10	
12:53:01	848	0.06	73													Recommence P4 from FL020	
12:53:55	828	0.06	73													FL030	
12:54:57	882	0.06	73													Interrupt P4 at FL038 start Run 11	
12:55:52	763	0.06	73													Recommence P4 from FL038	
12:57:20	927	0.06	73													FL050 (heaters on)	
12:58:12	1080	0.06	73													Interrupt P4 at FL060 start Run 12	
12:59:13	1478	0.06	73													Recommence P4	
13:00:18	884	0.06	73													FL070	
13:01:24	1204	0.06	73													FL080	
13:02:20	1394	0.06	73													FL090	
13:03:28	1403	0.06	73													FL100 End P4 Start run 13	
13:05:00	1442	0.06	73														
13:10:00	1007	0.06	73														
13:12:00	1212	0.06	73														
13:14:00	1158	0.06	73														
13:16:00	1086	0.06	73														
13:22:00	993	0.06	73														

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B 244

Date:

19/09/06 2006

Operator:

JT

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	Bottom inlet
----------------------------	-----------	--------------

Run No	Disk No 1	Disk No 2	Disk No 3	Top/Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
	TOP	MIDDLE	BOTTOM						
Transit	BLANK			Top	091350	093040		2635	Blanks to flush System
Transit	"			Bottom	091350	093040		2340	" "
Filters run1	49	134	37	Top	094653	102021		1060	Went through a little bit of Cloud.
Filters run1	71	80	159	Bottom	094653	102021		1189	
2	82	42	73	Top	102619	110343		1441	
2	156	80	159	Bottom	102619	110343		1372	
3	55	138	31	Top	111101	120044		1800 1907 1987	Got confused!
3	76	80	159	Bottom	111101	120044		1806 1806	
4	78	186	147	Top	120530	124520		1756	
4	43	80	159	Bottom	120530	124520		1515	
5	69	NL#3	3	Top	130336	133440		1469	
5	100	80	159	Bottom	130336	133440		940	
6	144	64	54	Top	133600			N/A	Closed to atmos & pump
6	46	80	159	Bottom	133600			N/A.	" " "
				Top					
				Bottom					
				Top					
				Bottom					
				Top					
				Bottom					
				Top					
				Bottom					

Flight No. B ~~2234~~ 243/244 ? Route

Date 19/9/06 Take Off 10:00

Bag Samplers: Debbie, Alan

Sheet No. 1

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
128	9:16:10	9:16:40			
535	9:17:00	9:17:40			
176	9:18:20	9:18:50			
366	9:19:20	9:19:50			
276	" 20:50	21:20			
305	" 21:50	22:50			
208	" 23:36	24:00			
293	" 24:30	25:00			
623	25:50	26:20			
39	26:50	27:20			
369	28:00	28:30			
438	29:00	29:30			
555	30:00	30:30			
49	31:00	31:30			
109	32:00	32:30			
37	33:00	33:30			
126	34:00	34:30			
110	35:00	35:30			
265	36:00	36:30			
391	37:00	37:33			
12	38:00	38:32			
97	43:00	42:30			
119	44:10	44:40			
3	45:00	45:30			
40 87	46:00	46:30			1000 ft. BC
40 64	47:00	47:30			"
40 828	48:00	48:30			"
40 40	49:00	49:30			"
612	50:00	50:30			"
499	51:00	51:30			"
322	52:00	52:30			"
211	53:00	53:30			"
625	54:00	54:30			"
106	55:00	55:30			"
121	56:00	56:30			"
84	57:00	57:30			"
252	58:00	58:30			"
354	59:00	59:30			"
2	10:00:00	10:00:30			"
526	10:07:00	10:07:30			"
5	02:00	02:30			"

Flight No. B243/244? Route

Date Take Off

Bag Samplers:

Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
243	10:02:00	10:03:30			1000ft RC
152	10:04:00	10:04:30			climbing to 5kft
47	10:05:00	10:05:30			climbing to 5kft
536	10:06:00	10:06:30			5kft
42	10:07:00	10:07:30			"
381	10:08:00	10:08:30			"
249	10:09:00	10:09:30			"
255	10:10:00	10:10:30			"
189	10:11:00	10:11:30			"
235	10:12:00	10:12:30			"
209	10:13:00	10:13:30			descent profile 1
172	10:14:00	10:14:30			"
145	15:00	15:30			"
89	16:00	16:30			"
180	17:00	17:30			2000ft run
02039	18:00	18:30			descent to 500ft
522	19:00	19:30			"
408	20:00	20:30			run at 500ft
352	21:00	21:30			descent to 200ft
91	22:00	22:30			"
78	23:00	23:30			"
239	24:00	24:30			profile 2 to 1000ft
515	25:00	25:30			run at 1000ft
521	26:00	26:30			
611	27:00	27:30			
327	28:00	28:30			
283	29:00	29:30			
87	30:00	30:30			
489	31:00	31:30			
349	32:00	32:30			
434	33:00	33:30			
8	34:00	34:30			
86	35:00	35:30			
452	36:00	36:30			
556	37:00	37:30			
82	38:00	38:30			
470	39:00	39:30			
230	40:00	40:30			
388	41:00	41:30			
88	42:00	42:30			
107	43:00	43:30			

Flight No. Route

Date Take Off

Bag Samplers:

Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
173	10:44:00	10:44:30			
173 53	10:45:05	10:45:30			
329	46:00	46:30			
233	47:00	47:30			
66	48:00	48:30			
40	49:00	49:30			
507	50:00	50:40			
177	51:00	51:30			
427	52:00	52:30			
187	53:00	53:30			
69	54:00	54:30			
424	55:00	55:30			
364	56:00	56:30			
592	57:00	57:30			
615	58:00	58:30			
171	59:00	59:30			
379	11:00:00	11:00:30			
279 26	11:07:00	11:07:30			
17	01:00	01:30			
17	03:00	03:30			
56	04:00	04:30			
63	05:00	05:30			
487	06:00	06:30			
505	07:00	07:30			
280	08:00	08:30			
530	09:00	09:30			
250	10:00	10:30			
18	11:00	11:30			
393	12:00	12:30			
484	13:00	13:30			
610	14:00	14:30			
220	15:00	15:30			
95	16:00	16:30			
74	17:00	17:30			
622	18:00	18:30			power station on coast (powerish)
51	19:00	19:30			a fire inland.
80	20:00	20:30			"
399	21:00	21:30			main urban (London).
50	22:00	22:30			
411	23:00	23:30			
246	24:00	24:30			

Flight No. Route

Date Take Off

Bag Samplers:

Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
182	11:25:00	11:25:30			
271	11:26:00	11:26:30			
387	27:00	27:30			
128	28:00	28:30			
7	29:00	29:30			
188	30:00	30:30			
425	31:00	31:30			
215	32:00	32:30			
460	33:00	33:30			
11	34:00	34:30			
396	35:00	35:30			
58600	36:00	36:30			
58	37:00	37:30			
14	38:00	38:30			
93	39:00	39:30			
32	40:10	40:45			
280	41:10	41:40			
551	42:00	42:30			
168	43:00	43:30			
251	44:00	44:30			
288	45:00	45:30			
454	46:00	46:30			
400 ?	47:00	47:30			
601 ?	48:00	48:30			
334 ?	49:00	49:30			
334	50:00	50:30			
48	51:00	51:30			
256	52:00	52:30			
245	53:00	53:30			
338	54:00	54:30			
258	55:00	55:30			
196	56:00	56:30			
137	57:00	57:30			
451	58:00	58:30			
314	59:00	59:30			
25	12:00:00	12:00:30			
217	01:00	01:30			
226	02:00	02:30			
464	03:00	03:30			
492	04:00	04:30			
529	05:00	05:30			

Flight No. Route

Date Take Off

Bag Samplers:

Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
302	12:06:00	12:06:30			cleaner air?
613	17:07:00	12:07:30			different air mass
360	08:00	08:30			
608	09:00	09:30			
614	10:00	10:30			
153	11:00	11:30			
114	12:00	12:30			
488	13:00	13:30			
186	14:00	14:30			shower inland
197	15:00	15:30			
385	16:00	16:30			
328	17:00	17:30			
500	18:00	18:30			
127	19:00	19:30			
60	20:00	20:30			
147	21:00	21:30			
204	22:00	22:30			
28	23:00	23:40			
205	24:10	24:40			
186	25:00	25:30			
13	26:00	26:30			
163	27:00	27:30			
290	28:00	28:30			
510	29:00	29:30			
218	30:00	30:30			
61	31:00	31:30			
282	32:00	32:30			
22	33:00	33:30			
361	34:00	34:30			
206	35:00	35:30			
503	36:00	36:30			
332	37:00	37:30			power station?
402	38:00	38:30			
266	39:00	39:30			
523	40:00	40:30			
132	41:00	41:30			
162	42:00	42:30			
73	43:00	43:30			
524	44:00	44:30			
195	45:00	45:30			profile descent
9	46:00	46:30			

Bag Sampling Log - DABEX

IAS, University of Leeds

Date: 19/9/06 Flight #: B244

Operator: Stephen Humphrey

Bag#	Start (UT)	End (UT)	Comments
57	9:24:34	45 second all time	Overland check - no pressure
58	9:30:22		--- " --- readings
59	9:45:57		Welsh coast
60	9:52:17		Severn Estuary
61	9:55:49		--- " ---
62	10:03:27		Devon coast
63	10:05:59		Devon overland FL55
64	10:09:39		--- " ---
49	10:22:10		E. Channel 250ft
50	10:29:45		--- " --- 1000ft
51	10:37:01	}	--- " --- Shipping lane
52	10:38:59		plume?
53	10:45:30		--- " --- 1000ft
54	10:54:05		--- " --- off S. Eng coast
55	11:07:17		E. Channel - SHOREHAM POWER STATION Hi NOx.
56	11:14:52		E. Channel off Dover (SHIPLANE ?)
41	11:19:49		Hi CO/NOx reported
42	11:23:50		London Plume?
43	11:31:17		2nd London Plume??
44	11:51:55		West of Norfolk
45	12:00:19		Plume - Scunthorpe area
46	12:03:44		Humber Estuary
47	12:05:18		Hi CO
48	12:12:51		Port 80.

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B 244**

Date: 19 September 2006

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU	Y		<u>Probes</u>		
XR5M GPS	Y		FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS	Y		PCASP		Y
Satcom C	Y		2D-P	Y	N
Satcom H	Y		2D-C	Y	N
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope		
De-Iced Temp	Y		SID 1	Y	N
Non De-Iced	Y		SID 2	Y	N
Heimann	Y		HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	?	N
G. Eastern	Y		CIP100	?	N
J. Williams	Y				
Nevzorov	Y				
TWC	N				
FWVS	N		<u>Racks:</u>		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	N	
Upper Clear	N		CCN / CNC	N	
“ Red	N		CVI	N	
“ IR	N				
“ shims	N		<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	N		PSAP		N
“ Red	N		Nephelometer		Y
“ IR	N		Filters		Y
“ shims	N		AMS		Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
MARSS	N		CDP		Y
DEIMOS	N		SAW		Y
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS		Y
SWS	N		2BT O3		N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC		N
Ozone		Y	PEROXIDE		N
SO2		Y	Formaldehyde		N
NOX		Y	ADA		N
CO		Y	CPI		N
ORAC			NOxy		Y
PAN			PTRMS		N
PERCA		Y	Bag Sampling		Y
WAS		Y	Tube Sampling		N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B244

Date: 19 September 2006

Instruments

1. CGPS – Couldn't connect CGPS PC pre-flight, message "COM 1 Port failed not connecting. Access denied". Tried selecting COM 2 then okay.
2. General Eastern – CB very sticky, needs to be replaced.
3. WAS – ethernet cable u/s. FAAM supplied replacement pre-flight then okay
 - no power on rack pre-flight, found to be due to CB on Rack not made. CB sticky in operation
4. FFC – picture very indistinct (camera lens and window were cleaned yesterday).
5. TDLAS – Primary hard disk failed in flight
6. Filters – counts creeping up with pump switched off
7. CPC on AMS Rack – pc display crashed, restart then okay

Aircraft

1. Helmets and harnesses – can they stay on aircraft during security check? Raise at De-brief

Satcom H Calls - Nil

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 19/9/06

Flight No: B244

Pre-Flighter: Bob Wells

<u>Item</u>	<u>✓ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	✓	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
		<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>		
2	✓	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	Kate to rescue with N ₂
3	✓	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	AVAPS
5	✓	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
6	✓	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	EE CB draggy
7	✓	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	Kate
8	✓	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	Kate
9	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
10	✓	HORACE	Recording data	
11	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
12	✓	HORACE	Status Checked	
13	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
14	✓	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
15	✓	GPS	Checked	
16	✓	INU	Align	
17	✓	Cameras Pictures	Checked OK x 4	
18	✓	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked	
20	✓	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	✓	GE	Balance checked	
22	✓	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
23		FWVS	Set up	Not fitted
24	✓	Satcom C	Turnaround message OK	No
25	✓	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
26	✓	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	
27		CNC	Butanol filled	AMS
28		CGPS	Set up	
		<u>External</u>		
29	✓	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	Camera shows Z + 2 mins
30	✓	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	✓	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	✓	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	✓	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	✓	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35		Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	} Not Fitted
36		Upper BBRs	Domes cleaned - Avalon	
37	✓	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
38		Heimann	Lens checked OK	
39		TWC Cover	Fitted if required	Not fitted
40		Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41		Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42		Tools	Avalon informed	

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B244:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting processing completion
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
NOxy	No log is ever taken for NOxy

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	25 Sep 2006	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Downward Facing Cameras

3 x Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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